

Cross Sectional Prospective Observational Study on Impact of Non-Stress Test in Prediction of Pregnancy OutcomeMedha¹, S.K. Datta²¹Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, B.R. Singh Hospital & Centre for Medical Education & Research, Sealdah, Kolkata²Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, B.R. Singh Hospital & Centre for Medical Education & Research, Sealdah, Kolkata

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** This test is based on the principle that fetal heart rate accelerates in response to fetal movement, reflecting the connection between fetal neurological function and cardiovascular reflexes. As fetal compromise progresses, this association is one of the first to be disrupted.**Methods:** A study was conducted to evaluate the predictive value of the Non-Stress Test (NST) for fetal outcomes in high-risk pregnancies. The research was carried out on 100 women with high-risk pregnancies between 2014 and 2015 at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, B.R.S.H., Kolkata. The NST was performed using Cardiotocography (CTG) in accordance with the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidelines to predict favourable or adverse fetal.**Results:** Out of 100 patients as per NST result 22% were found non-reactive and 78% were found reactive. The risk of less liquor quantity was 2.01 times more for patients with non-reactive NST result as compared to the patients with reactive NST and risk was not significant. NICU admission was 2.5 times more for patients with non-reactive NST result as compared to the patient with reactive NST result Risk of death was 3.66 times more for patients with non-reactive NST result as compared to the patients with reactive NST results (OR=3.66 (0.22,61.11);p=0.91)and risk was not significant.**Conclusion:** Further studies are needed to set the validity and reliability standards for NST.**Keywords:** Non stress test, Fetal heart rate, Fetal movement.

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Introduction

NST is used for fetal surveillance in high-risk pregnancies, including those with fetal growth restriction, multiple gestation, oligohydramnios, meconium-stained liquor (ACOG) [1].

During a non-stress test, the heart rate of a healthy, non-acidotic, and neurologically normal fetus will temporarily accelerate in response to fetal movement. This is considered a reliable indicator of normal fetal autonomic function. However, loss of reactivity can occur due to various factors, including: fetal sleep cycles, central nervous system depression, fetal acidosis. It's essential to note that loss of reactivity may not always indicate fetal distress, and further evaluation is necessary to determine the underlying cause.

Materials and Methods

This was a cross sectional prospective observational study done at the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, between 2014-2015. In this study 100 Labour, non-labour high risk cases were selected from both emergency and registered patients attending OPD and admitted in indoor. All cases were followed and NST was recorded weekly, biweekly, alternate days depending on the risk factors.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patient in reproductive age group with informed consent
2. Singleton pregnancies of 32 weeks or more of gestation
3. All high-risk pregnancies like IUGR, pre-eclampsia, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, decreased fetal movement, severe anaemia, post-

dated pregnancy immunisation, prom, advance maternal age >35 yrs., renal diseases, cardiac diseases, BOH.

Exclusion criteria

1. Gestational age of <32 weeks
2. anomalous babies detected by ultrasound scanning
3. antepartum haemorrhage, intrauterine death

Statistical analysis

It was performed with help of Epi info (TM) 3.5.3.x². Odds ratio (OR) with 95 % confidence interval (CI) was calculated to measure the different risk factors, significant level was 0.05. $p < 0.05$ was considered significant

Results

Table 1:

Risk factor	Number	%
Advance maternal age	8	8.0%
pre- eclampsia	20	20.0 %
GDM	9	9.0%
BOH	6	6.0%
Severe anemia	18	18.0%
Decreased fetal movement	11	11.0%
Prolonged pregnancy	8	8.0%
PROM	5	5.0%
IUGR	15	15.0%
Total	100	100%

Distribution of high-risk pregnancy: Most of the patients were with pre-eclampsia (20%) followed by severe anemia (18%), IUGR (15%), and decreased FM (11 %)

Table 2: Distribution of NST results

NST result	Number	%
Non-reactive	22	22.0%
Reactive	78	78.0 %
Total	100	100.0%

Out of 100 patients, 22 (22%) were found to have non-reactive Non-Stress Tests (NSTs), whereas 78 (78%) were found to have reactive NSTs.

Table 3: NST result of liquor quantity and liquor Colour

Liquor quantity	Non-reactive (n=22)	Reactive (n=78)	Total
Less	5 (22.7%)	10 (12.8%)	15
Normal	17(77.3%)	68(87.2%)	85
Total	24	76	100
Liquor Colour			
Meconium	4 (18.2%)	12 (15.4 %)	16
Normal	18 (81.8%)	66(84.6%)	84
Total	22	78	100
Apgar score at 5 minutes			
<7	2(9.1 %)	3(3.85)	5
>7	20(90.9%)	75(96.2%)	95
Total	22	78	100

The risk of less liquor quantity was 2.01 times more for patients with non-reactive NST result as compared to the patients with reactive NST and risk was not significant.

The risk of meconium-stained liquor was 1.22 times more for patients with non-reactive NST as compared to the patients with reactive NST, risk was not

significant. no significant association between Apgar score at 5 minute and groups ($p=0.65$) risk of Apgar score at 5 minutes <7 was 2.5 times more for patients with non-reactive NST results as compared to the patient with reactive NST, (OR=2.5(0.39,15.9); $p=0.65$), risk was not significant.

Table 4: NST result and birth weight, NICU admission, perinatal outcome

Birth weight	Non-reactive	Reactive	Total
Low birth weight	4(18.2%)	6(7.7%)	10
Normal	18(81.8%)	72(92.3%)	90
Total	22	78	100
NICU admission			
Yes	2(9.1%)	3(3.8%)	5
No	20(90.9%)	75(96.2%)	95
Perinatal outcome			
Died	1(4.5%)	1(1.3%)	2
Good	21(95.5%)	77(98.7%)	98
Total	22	78	100

Risk of low birth weight was 2.66 times more for patients with non-reactive NST results as compared to the patients with reactive NST result (OR=2.66 (0.68,10.45);P=0.29) whereas $X^2=0.19$ showed that no significant association between NICU admission and groups (p=0.65) and NICU admission was 2.5 times more for patients with non-reactive NST result as compared to the patient with reactive NST result.

Risk of death was 3.66 times more for patients with non-reactive NST result as compared to the patients with reactive NST results (OR=3.66 (0.22,61.11); p=0.91) and risk was not significant

Discussion

NST provides considerable information on well-being. The principle of this test is that it gives an indication via cerebro-cardiac response of fetal cerebral activity that is fetal hypoxia modified in the presence of hypoxia. The presence of meconium in the amniotic fluid was considered to be a sign of fetal hypoxia in the study Apgar score was <7 at 1 minute among the babies of abnormal NST group than normal NST that was similar to the study done by Wong SF, Chow KM, Ho LC (98% vs 6.4%). Shiekh SM Kamruddin A, Senta F, Riaz T [3] found that Apgar score <7 at 1 minute in 34 (64.15%), while it was >7 at 1 minute in 19 (35.84%). low Apgar score persisted at 5 minute in 10 (18.86%) cases of pathological CTG.

NO significant association was found between a pathological NST recording, fetal APGAR Score and acidemia, if pathological trace is used alone to assess fetal wellbeing. there 3 out of 78 normal NST infants and 2 out of 22 abnormal NST infants were admitted into NICU and showed that there was no significant association between NICU admission and groups (p=0.65). proportion of perinatal death was higher in NR group(4.5%) as compared to R group(1.3%). so sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value of perinatal outcome was 50.0%, 78.5%, 4.5%, 96.1% respectively.

Sensitivity of NST in perinatal outcome was 50.0%, specificity and NPV in our study are

78.5% and 96.1% respectively. Salamalekis E [4] assess the predictability of NST (reactive or nonreactive) in terms of fetal outcome, and concluded that a reactive test was found to be good predictor of the healthy fetus (NPV=91.2%), specificity was found to be 85.4%. Ienstrup C, Haase N [5] did a study on predictive value of antepartum fetal heart rate non-stress test in high risk pregnancy. They found that a total of 454 women with high risk pregnancies 95% NST results were normal, whereas 4% with slight pathological and 1% had severe pathological NST results. The frequency of perinatal morbidity was almost the same, irrespective of whether the NSTs showed accelerations or not on one or more occasions.

Conclusion

The routine practice of NST at delivery to exclude diagnosis of fetal stress is not an efficient tool to monitor the fetal outcome, although it is quick test but not an accurate method, doppler study, continuous recording of fetal heart rate, should be used over NST for fetal assessment.

Further studies are needed to set the validity and reliability standards for NST.

Ethical approval: The study was approved by the institutional ethics committee

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